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BATHYMETRIC SURVEY AND VOLUMETRIC ANALYSIS OF ASA DAM FOR SUSTAINABLE WATER RESOURCE MANAGEMENT IN KWARA STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract: *This study presents a bathymetric survey and volumetric analysis of a section of Asa Dam, located approximately 5 km south of Ilorin in Kwara State, Nigeria. The study aimed to generate bathymetric charts and determine the reservoir's volume to support effective water resource management. Field data acquisition involved establishing a vertical datum using a Hi-target Differential GPS receiver, water level measurement was carried out using an automatic level, and depth sounding using the Garmin EchoMAP 50dv echo sounder mounted on a survey boat. The collected data were processed and analyzed using a combination of Garmin Homeport, Surfer, AutoCAD, Esurvey CAD, Franson coordinate converter, and ArcGIS software. Different software was used in computing and cross-validating the reservoir volume, yielding values of approximately 2,074,442.70 m³, 2,024,444.16 m³, and 2,075,191.45 m³. Generated outputs include bathymetric charts, contour maps, and digital elevation models, revealing an irregular underwater topography. The study revealed the importance of regular bathymetric monitoring for sustainable reservoir management and future development planning. This study provides critical baseline data essential for decision-making and ecological preservation in Asa Dam.*

Keywords: Bathymetry, Volumetric Analysis, Digital Elevation Model (DEM), Reservoir Sedimentation, Water Resource Management

INTRODUCTION

Bathymetric surveying is an essential scientific discipline focusing on the measurement and mapping of underwater topography in oceans, seas, rivers, lakes, and reservoirs (Ferreira *et al.*, 2022). This survey process provides a detailed depiction of the underwater terrain, typically by recording depth contours, which is pivotal for various applications, including navigation safety, environmental monitoring, hydrological studies, water resource

management, engineering projects, and ecological conservation (Li *et al.*, 2023; Loureiro *et al.*, 2024). International Hydrographic Organization (IHO) defined hydrography as "the branch of applied science that deals with measurements and description of the physical features of oceans, seas, coastal areas, lakes and rivers, as well as with the prediction of their changes over time, for the primary purpose of safety of navigation and in support of all marine activities, including economic

development, security and defense, scientific research, and environmental protection" (Ojinnaka, 2007). This broad definition underscores hydrography's integral role in a wide range of disciplines related to water bodies and their management.

Hydrography and its subfield, bathymetry, have evolved significantly with advances in technology. Bathymetry, defined as the science of measuring and charting depths to determine the topography of the seafloor and other aquatic bodies, employs data gathered from diverse sources such as aircraft, surface ships, satellites, submersibles, and underwater platforms (Wölfl *et al.*, 2019; Ferreira *et al.*, 2022). A bathymetric survey is critical for proper water allocation and management in a reservoir (Ipadeola *et al.*, 2024). This modern approach allows for a precise representation of underwater features that were previously unattainable with traditional hydrographic methods. Bathymetric surveys generate maps with depth contours (isobaths) analogous to the elevation contours used in terrestrial topographic maps. However, instead of lines connecting points of equal elevation above sea level, bathymetric maps connect points of equal depth below the water surface, a key distinction that aids in understanding underwater terrain (Ferreira *et al.*, 2022; Li *et al.*, 2023).

The significance of bathymetric surveys is multifaceted. Beyond providing depth information for safe navigation, bathymetry supports volumetric analysis needed for effective reservoir management, especially in monitoring sedimentation rates, sediment deposition patterns, and water storage capacity over time (Oladosu *et al.*, 2019; Mekonnen *et al.*, 2022). Reservoir sedimentation reduces the usable water volume, impacting the reliability of the water supply and the sustainability of the dam. Therefore, consistent monitoring via bathymetric surveys

is essential for sustainable management and infrastructure maintenance. Pre- and post-dredging bathymetric charts help ascertain dredged volumes and guide maintenance activities.

This study targets the Asa Dam in Ilorin, Kwara State, Nigeria. The dam is a vital water resource project. Given the dam's importance, detailed knowledge of its underwater topography and storage capacity is imperative (Sanda, 2018; Olawumi, 2022); hence, the bathymetric survey and volumetric analysis of a section of the dam. This is with the view to suggest an appropriate water resource management that will ensure the reservoir operational efficiency, sediment control, and ecological balance. The integration of different technologies and software in this study strengthens the robustness of the volumetric estimates, accounting for the non-uniform bottom topography as revealed by the bathymetric data. This study will not only contribute to the technical understanding of Asa Dam's morphology but also serve as a reference for improved planning, sediment management, and sustainable utilization. The outcome of the study will support scientists, engineers, dam operators, and policymakers in the effective stewardship of Asa Dam, ensuring continued water availability and ecological health for the city of Ilorin and its environs.

THE STUDY AREA

The study area is Asa Dam, located in Ilorin, the capital city of Kwara State, Nigeria. Geographically, Asa Dam lies between latitudes 8°25'30.55" and 8°26'22.82" North and longitudes 4°32'13.04" and 4°33'20.79" East. Positioned at the upstream segment of the Asa River, the dam is situated within a tropical savanna climate characterized by distinct wet seasons, with annual rainfall ranging from 990 to 1,318 mm and average

temperatures around 28°C. This climate promotes rainfall-driven erosion that significantly impacts sediment transport (Olawumi, 2022; Bello, 2023).

The soils in the area are predominantly coarse, sandy, and derived from Basement Complex rocks, making them highly susceptible to erosion and facilitating sediment mobilization into the reservoir (Sanda, 2018). Land use includes residential, commercial, agricultural, and vegetative areas, where disturbed soils and urbanization increase runoff and erosion, further contributing to sediment yield (Bello, 2023; Ipadeola & Babalola, 2025). These factors collectively influence sediment generation, leading to accumulation in Asa Dam, which alters its bed topography and reduces storage capacity, posing challenges to

sustainable water resource management in Kwara State (Bello, 2023).

Asa Dam comprises three sections: a 400 m earth-fill dam, a 150 m concrete gravity dam, and a 160 m lateral earth dam, with heights ranging from 6 m to 26 m. It includes a 60-meter-wide spillway designed to discharge approximately 1,300 cubic meters per second. The dam serves as a critical water supply source for Ilorin and surrounding communities, underscoring the need for precise bathymetric surveys and volumetric analysis to support effective management and sustainable use (Sanda, 2018; Olawumi, 2022). Due to the dam's complex reservoir and diverse underwater topography, detailed hydrographic investigations are essential to inform planning and resource management decisions.

Figure 1: The study area
Source: Authors (2025)

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study employed an integrated approach combining precise field data collection with advanced spatial data processing to conduct a bathymetric survey and volumetric analysis of Asa Dam. The methodology encompassed equipment selection, systematic data acquisition, and robust data processing to ensure accurate mapping of underwater topography and reservoir volume estimation.

EQUIPMENT AND FIELD DATA COLLECTION

Bathymetric data were acquired using a Garmin EchoMAP 50dv echo sounder mounted on a survey boat, which continuously transmitted acoustic pulses to measure water depth by recording the time interval for echoes reflected from the dam bed. The transducer was securely affixed to the boat via a transducer pole to maintain consistent depth measurements. Water level readings relative to a fixed vertical benchmark (mean sea level) were obtained using a Sokkia digital automatic level and leveling staffs to establish a reliable reference datum. Horizontal positioning employed a GPS receiver to record precise GPS coordinates at each sounding point. Ancillary measurements were conducted using calibrated tapes to support spatial accuracy. The survey followed systematically planned transects across the reservoir to ensure comprehensive spatial coverage. Personnel safety was upheld through standard safety equipment, including life jackets, and all field operations were thoroughly documented.

DATA PROCESSING AND SPATIAL ANALYSIS

Post-collection data processing involved water level correction, wherein raw depths were reduced to chart datum using the formula $RL = BM + BS - FS$ (where RL is reduced level, BM is benchmark height, BS is backsight reading, and FS is foresight reading). Depth data underwent error filtering and coordinate transformation through Garmin Homeport and Franson Coordinate Converter software (Lubczonek *et al*, 2021). The cleaned bathymetric datasets were interpolated using ArcGIS's "Topo to Raster" tool to produce a high-resolution Digital Elevation Model (DEM) representing three-dimensional underwater terrain variations.

To enhance the accuracy and reliability of volumetric assessments, reservoir volumes were calculated independently using multiple software platforms and methodologies. Surfer software applied numerical integration methods (trapezoidal and Simpson's rules) to depth grids, Esurvey CAD employed sectional area integration based on coordinate cross-sections, and ArcGIS utilized its Surface Volume tool referencing the DEM. Comparison and cross-validation of volume outputs ensured methodological robustness and confidence in resultant reservoir capacity estimates.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The bathymetric survey of Asa Dam yielded geospatial datasets that facilitated the production of various maps and volumetric analyses critical for effective water resource management. Key outputs included the bathymetric chart, contour map, 3D surface map, 3D wireframe, and Digital Elevation Model (DEM). Each of the images provided unique visualizations of the dam's underwater topography.

MAPS AND SPATIAL VISUALIZATIONS

The bathymetric chart (Figure 2) revealed the depth distribution within the dam, showing significant variability rather than a flat bottom. This corresponds closely with the contour map (Figure 3), which displays isobaths connecting points of equal depth,

emphasizing the non-uniform underwater terrain. The 3D surface (Figure 4) and wireframe model (Figure 5) further illustrates the complexity of the dam bed topography, allowing for a three-dimensional understanding of depth variations (Ipadeola *et al.*, 2024). The DEM generated through ArcGIS (Figure 6) offered a precise raster representation of the underwater landscape, serving as the foundation for volumetric computations.

Figure 2: Bathymetric chart of Asa Dam

Source: Authors (2025)

Figure 3: Contour map of the study area
Source: Authors (2025)

Figure 4: 3D Surface map of the study area
Source: Authors (2025)

Figure 5: Showing 3D wireframe of the area (Researchers, 2025)
Source: Authors (2025)

Figure 6: Digital Elevation Model of the study Area
Source: Authors (2025)

VOLUMETRIC ANALYSIS

Volume calculation was performed using multiple software tools to enhance reliability through cross-validation. The Surfer software used three different numerical integration techniques of Trapezoidal Rule, Simpson's Rule, and Simpson's 3/8 Rule to compute the current reservoir volume as 2,075,947.30 m³, 2,074,442.70 m³, and 2,075,088.36 m³, respectively. Among these results, the Simpson's Rule is deemed the most accurate because it carefully considers both terminal and intermediate ordinates in the volume integration process (Birko *et al.*, 2024). Consequently, the accepted volume estimate from Surfer was set at 2,074,442.70 m³.

Using Esurvey CAD, the volume was determined by sectional area integration across regular coordinate intervals, resulting in a volume estimate of 2,024,444.16 m³. This method involves calculating the area for sequential sections and summing them to obtain the total volume, offering a spatially explicit volumetric assessment.

ArcGIS's Surface Volume tool computed the reservoir volume based on the DEM, estimating the volume as 2,075,191.45 m³. This method benefits from advanced spatial interpolation and surface modeling capabilities inherent in ArcGIS for highly accurate volumetric estimation (Habib *et al.*, 2020)

COMPARATIVE ASSESSMENT OF THE SOFTWARE USED

The volumes computed across the three software platforms demonstrate close agreement, with minor differences attributed to the inherent methodologies and interpolation algorithms (Garnero & Godone, 2014). The largest discrepancy of approximately 49,998.54 m³ was observed between Surfer and Esurvey CAD, while comparatively smaller differences were observed between ArcGIS and Surfer (748.75 m³), and ArcGIS and

Esurvey CAD (50,747.29 m³). The average volume across all methods is approximately 2,058,026.10 m³, reinforcing the consistency and robustness of the calculated reservoir capacity.

The non-planar nature of the dam bed, as illustrated by the bathymetric charts and DEM, underscores the necessity of using these sophisticated computational techniques rather than simplistic planar assumptions for volume estimation. Such accuracy is essential for sustainable reservoir management, sedimentation studies, and water allocation planning.

IMPLICATIONS FOR RESEARCH FINDINGS FOR WATER RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

The bathymetry and volume analyses provide vital baseline data for monitoring sediment deposition and water storage capacity over time. Regular updates to bathymetric maps facilitated by these methods will enable monitoring of sediment accumulation rates and volume reduction, which potentially indicates reservoir aging (Mekonnen *et al.*, 2022; Hilgert *et al.*, 2024). Understanding sediment dynamics through such study like this can guide dredging operations, structural maintenance, and ecological preservation efforts within the Asa Dam catchment (Sanda, 2018).

This comprehensive assessment of Asa Dam's underwater topography and volume contributes to enhance physical planning, decision-making, and enhanced strategies tailored to the dam's unique morphometric characteristics. Importantly, it equips managers with quantitative tools to mitigate risks associated with sedimentation and reduced water capacity, ensuring the dam's continued functionality and ecological balance for surrounding communities.

This comprehensive bathymetric and volumetric assessment provides essential baseline data for monitoring sediment deposition, reservoir capacity, and flow dynamics over time. The maps and volume computations support effective physical planning, sustainable management, and future upgrade decisions for Asa Dam. Regular updates of these datasets can help identify sedimentation trends, inform dredging, and preserve ecological balance, benefiting the dam's operational lifespan and the downstream community.

The integration of diverse software and field data in this study highlights the value of multi-method approaches to reservoir analysis, providing reliable data critical for decision-making in water resources management.

CONCLUSION

This study provides critical baseline data on Asa Dam's underwater topography and reservoir volume, essential for sustainable water resource management. The integration of advanced bathymetric surveying and volumetric analysis techniques offers reliable insights into sedimentation patterns and reservoir capacity changes. These findings support informed decision-making for sediment control, reservoir maintenance, and ecological preservation. Regular updates and monitoring are recommended to sustain the dam's functionality and benefit local

communities. This research contributes a valuable framework applicable to similar reservoirs for improved management and planning.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The study recommends:

- 1) Water Resource Managers and Dam Operators are enjoined to conduct regular and comprehensive bathymetric surveys covering all sections of Asa Dam to ensure complete and up-to-date data for effective reservoir management.
- 2) Upgrade and the maintenance of high-quality surveying instruments to improve the accuracy and reliability of bathymetric and volumetric measurements is re
- 3) The bathymetric and sedimentation data should be used by Environmental and Ecological Agencies to inform ecological preservation strategies and sediment control measures within the Asa Dam catchment.
- 4) Support annual bathymetric monitoring programs should be sponsored by the Policy Makers and Government, aimed at tracking changes in water volume and sediment deposition, enabling timely interventions such as dredging and infrastructure maintenance.

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